

THE STUDY OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: This article defines role of intercultural communication in society and analyses reasons why intercultural communication is important This works also includes information about the term culture. Intercultural communication is correspondence between individuals with contrasting social personalities. Culture and character are made, comprehended, and changed through intercultural correspondence. Business is almost borderless, so it's important to learn how to communicate effectively and respectfully with people from other cultures. Studying intercultural communication can also help you become more self-aware.

Key words: communication, essential skill, different countries, misunderstandings, culture, multiculturalism.

Intercultural competence covers a large field ranging from linguistic aspects all the way to social and cultural conventions. It's important to be aware that each culture may have different social conventions. American business partners, for example, prefer small talk to build a relationship first, whereas Brits may try humor, and Germans tend to get straight to the point without beating around the bush. Thais, on the other hand, think nothing of asking what are considered rather personal questions in the western world, for example about your marital status or job. Similarly, Americans like to use first names when addressing others, while in Austria, titles should be used to avoid sounding disrespectful. Germans will want to shake hands, while people in Thailand place their palms together at chest level and bow instead.

What makes intercultural communication so important?

There are many reasons why intercultural communication is important. First of all, effective intercultural communication is an essential skill for anyone working across different countries or regions in order to establish harmonious relationships and avoid conflict. It is essential to accurately and appropriately transfer information across countries and cultures. Executives in multinational companies, working either in their home country or as expats abroad, especially benefit from great intercultural communication skills to engage with international clients and employees.

Similarly, intercultural communication is also crucial for anyone working with people from other cultures to avoid misunderstandings and even offense. It's fair to say that intercultural communication is the foundation for successful international business in today's globalized world.

Intercultural communication is correspondence between individuals with contrasting social personalities. Culture and character are made, comprehended, and changed through intercultural correspondence. Business is almost borderless, so it's important to learn how to communicate effectively and respectfully with people from other cultures. Studying intercultural communication can also help you become more self-aware (Martin & Nakayama, 2010). Your way of thinking about culture is frequently "other focused," which means that the culture of the other person or group is what stands out to you. However, as you gain a deeper understanding of other cultures and points of view, the adage "know thyself" becomes more relevant. You may be able to see your culture through a different perspective by stepping outside of your familiar, comfortable frame of reference through intercultural communication. As you challenge your ethnocentrism, or tendency to view your own culture as superior to other cultures, you may also become more ethical communicators as you become more self-aware. The video below provides strategies for developing cultural competence and provides an explanation of cultural competence.

The term "culture" is used to describe this aspect of having a meaningful collective existence. Culture is the set of symbols that people use to come up with solutions to real-world problems. We understand that human experience is primarily cultural or meaningful in this context. The meanings that people give to things, actions, other people, and themselves are essential to human social life. People do not, in a sense, live in close proximity to the outside world and each other; Instead, the shared meanings provided by culture serve as their only means of indirect life. The experience of culture is this mediated experience.¹

Patterns of learned and shared behavior that are cumulative and passed down through generations can be referred to as culture. The systematic and predictable ways that people in a culture act or think can be seen as patterns. People's thoughts, feelings, and beliefs are reflected in patterns. Cultural information adaptation, sharing, and storage produce these patterns. Cultural differences and similarities in patterns are possible. For instance, it is considered courteous to bring a small present to the home of a host in both India and Canada. Bringing a bottle of wine and expecting it to be

¹ Lustig, M.W. & Koester, J. (2007). Intercultural competence: Interpersonal communication across cultures (5th ed.) Shanghai, China . Shanghai Foreign Language education Press.

opened right away is more common in Canada. In contrast, gifts of sweets are more common in India, where they are frequently kept for later consumption.

People create culture by sharing with one another. Humans collaborate with others in their networks and share knowledge and skills. Culture is made up of the ways people share and the things they share. For instance, older adults recall a time when letters sent every few months were used to keep up long-distance friendships. Using instant text messages on smartphones, contemporary youth culture achieves the same objective.

Because parents and caregivers are the primary influence on young children, enculturation—the process by which behaviors, values, and norms are acquired—starts with them. Parental figures show kids, both straightforwardly and as a visual cue, about how to act and how the world functions. They remind children to say "Thank you" and encourage them to be polite. Kids are taught how to dress in a way that fits the culture.

The superficial signs that provide some indications of cultural expression are easy to mistake for culture. However, an adaptation of Edward Hall's original is called "Culture is much deeper than the eye can see," and it is frequently used to help people see the hidden depths of culture.

Despite the fact that they are frequently used interchangeably, it is essential to distinguish between the terms referring to culture.

First, intrapersonal communication, which may also be intracultural due to the fact that you only represent one culture, refers to communication with oneself. However, the majority of people are part of multiple groups, each with its own culture. Consider, for instance, a person who lives in Ontario but travels to Quebec for business. She starts to impart verbally in French. If she speaks French well, she might then find that she often thinks and talks to herself in that language. Certainly, the language in this instance reflects the culture and evokes lived experience, influencing how thoughts are formed and the expressions used. A conversation with oneself can occasionally reveal competing objectives, needs, wants, or values. How did you find out about those values or goals? In a similar vein, you might consider your struggle to be an intercultural conflict if you find it difficult to meet the demands and standards set by various groups.

Multiculturalism is both a way of thinking about and managing cultural diversity and the diversity of cultures within a single territory. Multiculturalism is a policy that aims to address the inevitability of cultural tensions while simultaneously promoting and acknowledging cultural differences. The following four issues are identified by opponents of multiculturalism:

Multiculturalism just cursorily acknowledges the equity, everything being equal; For instance, Canada only has two official languages.

Stereotyping occurs because multiculturalism forces minority individuals to assume the limited cultural identities of their ethnic group of origin.

Minorities who do not fully integrate into Canadian society are kept apart by multiculturalism's ideal.

Constitutional safeguards for individual rights are undermined by multiculturalism's emphasis on group rights.

"Cross-cultural approaches typically go a bit deeper, with the goal of being more diplomatic or sensitive," Old's College states. Through trade and cooperation, they account for some interaction and recognition of differences, which builds some limited understanding. For instance, they bow instead of shaking hands or give small but meaningful gifts. Sadly, not all of them are well-rounded comparisons; If we aren't careful, cross-cultural comparisons can lead to stereotyping and ethnocentric attitudes, in which we judge other cultures based on our own cultural standards.

On the other hand, societies that are intercultural show a deep understanding of and respect for differences. In an intercultural society, people grow and learn from each other. The society's interactions are based on acceptance rather than tolerance and result in the exchange of ideas and social norms for the purpose of developing deeper relationships. Intercultural relationships must be developed for sustained growth and cooperation for businesses to succeed in the global economy. Mindful intercultural communication, which will be discussed below, is one way to accomplish this.

Intercultural communication finally, refers to exchanges taking place between different cultures.

So, in a nutshell, intercultural communication relates to interactions among people from different cultures, while cross-cultural communication involves comparing interactions among people from the same culture to those from another culture.

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